

Chemical Investigation of *Artemisia vulgaris* L.

S. K. Kundu*, (Mrs.) A. Chatterjee and A. S. Rao

From the petrol extractives of *Artemisia vulgaris* L. (—) thujone, α -amyrin and its acetate, fernenol—a new pentacyclic triterpene alcohol, stigmasterol and β -sitosterol have been isolated in pure state. The presence of α and β -pinenes was indicated by GLC analysis. The occurrence of a ketone, m.p. 78°, an alcohol, m.p. 56°, and three hydrocarbons, designated as hydrocarbons *A*, *B* and *C* has also been observed in the petrol extract of the plant materials.

The plant *Artemisia vulgaris* L. (locally known as Titapati for its extreme bitterness) (Fam : Compositae) has wide varieties and grows abundantly throughout the mountainous districts of India. It is frequently used in folk medicine for its stomachic, deobstruent, antispasmodic and anthelmintic properties.^{1,2}

Santonin, the powerful anthelmintic is obtained from the plant *Artemisia maritima*. However, in Indian soil it fails to produce the desired santonin, plausibly due to ecological variation. Therefore to find out a suitable substitute for *A. maritima* an elaborate survey was made which resulted in the discovery of wild and colossal occurrence of *A. vulgaris* in the Himalayan region. With a view to exploring its economic utilisation systematic investigation has been undertaken. From the same botanical species of Australian origin Geissman *et al.*³ have isolated a sesquiterpene lactone-vulgarin. Further work on this species by other workers has revealed interesting informations. Carbohydrates were found to be present in this plant^{4,5}. From the unsaponifiable matter in the leaf lipids of this species, β -sitosterol and 12-tetracosanol has been isolated by Matsamoto⁶ and from the hairy leaves of this plant Fujita *et al.*⁷ isolated 2–3% of a wax which yielded on saponification hentriacontane, 1-eicosanol and 12-tricosanol. A number of polyacetylenic compounds have been reported in this plant.^{8–10} Recently P. S. Rao *et al.*¹¹ reported the presence of *p*-cymene, linalool, β -thujene, azulene, β -thujyl alcohol, free and combined, and an unidentified hydrocarbon in the steam-distilled oil of this plant. A number of lactones having an eudesmanic carbon skeleton have been previously isolated from a variety of *Artemisia* species.

* Present address : Dept. of Chemistry, University of Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania 15213, U.S.A.

1. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayar and I. C. Chopra, Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants, C.S.I.R., p. 26 (1956).
2. K. B. Kirtikar and B. D. Basu, Indian Medicinal Plants, p. 700 (1918 Edition).
3. T. A. Geissman and G. A. Ellested, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **27**, 1864.
4. Henri Colin, *Compt. rend.*, 1935, **201**, 1414.
5. Hitoshi Ono, *Kyushu Mem. Med. Sci.*, 1952, **3**, No. 1, 27.
6. T. Matsumoto and I. Niiya, *Nippon Daigaku Kogaku Kenkyunsho*, 1956, No. 13, 103.
7. A. Fujita and T. Yoshikawa, *J. Pharm. Soc. (Japan)*, 1953, **73**, 464.
8. F. Fohlman, E. Inhoffen and P. Henbest, *Chem. Ber.*, 1957, **90**, 124 1661
9. K. Stavolt and N. A. Sorenson, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1950, **4**, 1567.
10. F. Fohlman and H. J. Mannhardt, *Chem. Ber.*, 1955, **88**, 361, 429.
11. P. S. Rao, and V. K. Sood, *Perfumerie Und Kosmetik*, 1964, **45**, 63.

The present communication reports the isolation and the characterisation of the chemical constituents of *A. vulgaris* which could be procured through the courtesy of Dr. K. P. Biswas*, Director, Medicinal Plants Committee, West Bengal, India.

The dried plant on extraction with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) at room temperature and removal of solvent at 40° under vacuum** afforded a highly viscous dark coloured extract named "Oil of Artemisia". This is bitter in taste, having a typical odour, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$; saponification value, 84. The oil, on treatment with methanol separated a solid which after purification by repeated chromatography (TLC pure) afforded a white solid***, m.p. 78°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$. Its IR spectrum (ν_{max} 1724 cm^{-1}) and very weak absorption in the region around 280 $\text{m}\mu$, and negative tetranitromethane test concluded the presence of a saturated ketone. But it fails to form any ketonic derivatives like semi-carbazone or 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone under usual conditions. The mother liquor after the separation of the ketone was chromatographed over alumina and eluted successfully from less polar to more polar solvents (vide experimental). Four major fractions (A, B, C and D) were collected. A was subjected to fractional distillation and crystallisation of residual solid furnished a crystalline compound (TLC pure), m.p. 64°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$. Elemental analysis, infrared spectrum, absence of yellow colour with tetranitromethane and negative absorption in the region, 220–340 $\text{m}\mu$ indicated it to be a saturated hydrocarbon† (Hydrocarbon A).

The fraction B on treatment with ethylacetate and cooling to -15° separated another crop of ketone, m.p. 78°, obtained earlier. The mother liquor on chromatography and fractional distillation of the petroleum ether eluate afforded a liquid (88% pure by VPC). The IR spectrum showed the presence of a cyclopentanone (bands at 1740 cm^{-1}) and a cyclopropane ring (bands at 3522, 3552 cm^{-1}) in its molecule. It formed a semicarbazone, m.p. 186–87°, $[\alpha]_D + 58^\circ$; 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 116°, $[\alpha]_D + 44^\circ$. Elemental analysis of the ketone, m.p. 78°, its semicarbazone and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative indicated the molecular formula of the ketone to be $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ and the presence of cyclopentanone and cyclopropane rings in its molecule suggested its identity with thujone†† (II). This was

* Retired since 1964.

** Certain terpenic compounds polymerise on heating and hence the temperature was carefully controlled.

*** It is interesting to note that 12-tricosanol, a constituent of *Artemisia vulgaris* L. is reported⁷ to furnish 12-tricosanone, m.p. 79.5°, on oxidation with CrO_3 -acetic acid. The ketone, m.p. 78° isolated by us may be 12-tricosanone as evidenced from an examination of its properties.

† Recently Rangaswami *et al.*¹² has isolated a hydrocarbon, m.p. 63–65°, from *Sterum princeps* Jung and indicated it to be a mixture of C_{27} , C_{29} and C_{31} paraffins¹³. The compound, m.p. 64° isolated from *Artemisia vulgaris* L. may be of similar nature. Incidentally, the isolation of hentriacontane, $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{64}$, m.p. 68.5° from *Artemisia vulgaris* L. has also been reported by Fujita⁷.

12. Rangaswami and Pratap Singh, *Curr. Sci.*, 1966, 205.

13. Piper *et al.*, *Biochem. J.*, 1931, 2086.

†† The IR spectra of authentic (–) thujone and (+) isothujone were kindly furnished by Prof. R. H. Eastman, Stanford University, California and NMR spectra have been reproduced by K. Tori¹⁶.

supported from a direct comparison of their IR and NMR spectra and also by its oxidation with KMnO_4 ¹⁴ to the known crystalline keto-carboxylic acid (IV), m.p. 75–76°, $[\alpha]_D + 214^\circ$. During the course of this investigation it was revealed that pure (–) thujone semicarbazone on treatment with oxalic acid under usual conditions yielded a mixture of about 80% of (–) thujone (II) and 20% of (+) isothujone (III).

However, if the hydrolysis of (–) thujone semicarbazone is carried out with $2(\text{N})\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ at 20° in a suspension of petrol ether as employed in β -cyclocitral series¹⁵, the isomerisation can be totally avoided and pure (–) thujone would be the sole product. Similarly, pure (+) isothujone under identical conditions afforded pure (+) isothujone. An interesting observation has been made in this connection. “Thujone fraction” obtained by employing fractionation but avoiding repeated chromatography had $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$, whereas thujone fraction isolated after repeated chromatography on alumina* showed $[\alpha]_D + 25^\circ$. This indicates that the ketone present in the plant of *Artemisia vulgaris* L. is (–) thujone¹⁶ which is gradually epimerised to an equilibrium mixture during chromatography. The low boiling fraction B_8 (vide Chart I) obtained during the separation of thujone by fractional distillation, was found to be a mixture of six compounds, two of them being identified as α and β -pinenes by VPC, the third one as thujone. The other three could not be characterised.

The high boiling fraction (B_8) obtained during the fractional distillation of “Thujone fraction” on keeping with petrol ether at 0° separated a crystalline solid (TLC and VPC pure), m.p. 56°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$. Elemental analysis, absence of yellow colour with tetranitromethane, lack of absorption in the region 220–340 $m\mu$ suggested its saturated nature. Its IR spectrum (ν_{max} 3344 cm^{-1}) shows that it is an alcohol. The alcoholic group appears to be tertiary in nature since it does not undergo oxidation with Jones Reagent¹⁷ or with CrO_3 -pyridine complex.¹⁸ However, it formed an acetate (ν_{max} 1745, 1235 cm^{-1}) on treatment with acetic anhydride-pyridine at 50° for 24 hr. The mother liquor after the separation of alcohol, m.p. 56° from B_8 was fractionated. The fraction, b.p. 140–65°/0.3 mm., on purification by chromatography over alumina followed by distillation over sodium afforded a hydrocarbon (hydrocarbon B) (tested pure by TLC and VPC), b.p. 130–140°/0.3 mm. $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$, n_D ²⁷ 1.469. Elemental analysis, UV, IR and NMR spectra suggested it to be a

14. F. Tieman and F. W. Semmler, *Chem. Ber.*, 1897, **30**, 429; D. Thomson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **97**, 1501.

* Acid washed, grade II alumina (Brockmann).

15. W. G. Young and S. L. Linden, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2072.

16. K. Tori, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1964, **12**, 1439.

17. A. Bowers, T. G. Halsall, E. R. H. Jones and A. J. Lemin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2548.

see also C. Djerassi, R. R. Engle and A. Bowers, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, **21**, 1547.

18. J. J. Poos, G. E. Arth, R. E. Beyler and L. H. Sarrett, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **151**, 442.

saturated hydrocarbon. The fraction B₉ was also found to be reasonably pure (VPC). It was further purified by chromatography over alumina and subsequent distillation over sodium. The hydrocarbon (hydrocarbon C) thus obtained was shown to be pure (by TLC and VPC) and had b.p. 140–50°/0.5 mm., $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$, n_D^{27} 1.458. Elemental analysis, IR (ν_{max} 990, 910 cm⁻¹), UV and NMR spectra indicated that it is an unsaturated hydrocarbon.

The undistilled portion B₁₀ showed a strong carbonyl absorption in the IR spectrum and in TLC showed one major spot. It was chromatographed over alumina. The petrol ether-benzene eluates gave a solid which on repeated crystallisation furnished crystals, m.p. 223–24°, $[\alpha]_D + 82^\circ$. Its IR spectrum (ν_{max} 1740, 1250 cm⁻¹) suggested the presence of an ester function (acetate). Elemental analysis and mass spectrum showed the molecular formula to be C₃₂H₅₂O₂ which corresponded to an acetate of a triterpene alcohol. An examination of its properties suggested it to be α -amyrin acetate which was shown to be correct by a direct comparison with an authentic sample by m.m.p., TLC (identical R_f) and superimposable IR spectra and also by its conversion on saponification to α -amyrin, m.p. 182–84°, $[\alpha]_D + 91^\circ$. The saponification product was found to be identical with α -amyrin following the usual procedure.

The alcohol-eluted fraction obtained after chromatography of fraction B₁₀ was found to contain one major component as indicated from TLC. The mixture was resolved on Tswett column using alumina. The benzene eluted fraction of the chromatogram afforded a solid which on repeated crystallisation furnished a new pentacyclic triterpene alcohol designated as fernenol, m.p. 194°, $[\alpha]_D - 24^\circ$, having modified hopane skeleton (V)¹⁹. The mother liquor after the crystallisation of fernenol was converted to its acetate and crystallised to give a crude acetate m.p. 175–85° which was saponified with 5% alcoholic KOH to yield crude fernenol. The latter on chromatographic resolution yielded fernenol which on crystallisation yielded another crop of pure fernenol. The mother liquor of fernenol was converted into its acetate which was further chromatographed. Elution of the chromatogram with petroleum ether afforded a solid which on repeated crystallisations furnished crystals, m.p. 223–24°, $[\alpha]_D + 82^\circ$, identical with α -amyrinacetate. This eventually established the presence of α -amyrin* in *Artemisia vulgaris* L.

19. S. K. Kundu, A. Chatterjee and A. S. Rao, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, 1043; *Austr. J. Chem.*, 1968, **21**, 1931; K. Nishimoto, M. Ito, S. Natori and T. Ohmoto, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Japan)*, 1966, **14**, 97.

* We thank Dr. V. K. Hinge, N.C.L., Poona-8 for his gift of authentic samples of α -amyrin and α -amyrin acetate.

* Since the alcohol eluted fraction B₂₁ contained only alcoholic and no carbonyl components (from IR), the isolation indicates the presence of α -amyrin in fraction B₂₁ i.e., in *Artemisia vulgaris* L.

The petroleum ether-benzene eluted fractions B₄ and C (Chart I) were found to be identical on the basis of their TLC and IR spectra and hence mixed together. It was kept with ethylacetate at -15° for 2 days. The resulting solid on repeated crystallisations, yielded shining crystals, m.p. 169-70°, [α]_D-50°. Elemental analysis indicated the molecular formula C₂₉H₄₈O. The IR spectrum showed the presence of a hydroxyl group (ν_{max} 3540 cm⁻¹) and it gives the usual colour test for sterols (Liebermann-Burchard). The compound was shown to be identical with stigmasterol by the usual procedure. On acetylation with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate, it gave an acetate m.p. 144-45°, [α]_D-55°, identical with stigmasterol acetate.

The mother liquor C, left after the separation of stigmasterol was chromatographed over alumina. The solid obtained in the pet. ether-benzene eluted fractions gave single spot in TLC and on repeated crystallisations afforded another crop of fernenol (identified by mixed m.p., TLC and IR spectra). The benzene-chloroform eluted fractions showed single spot in TLC having almost identical R_f with that of stigmasterol. Repeated crystallisation of the compound furnished needles of β-sitosterol, m.p. 136-37°, [α]_D-35°, as evidenced from elemental analysis (molecular formula, C₂₉H₅₀O), colour reactions of sterols (Liebermann-Burchard) and m.m.p., R_f value in TLC and superimposable IR spectra with an authentic sample of β-sitosterol.

The fractions B₅ and D (Chart I) were found to be a mixture of alcoholic components (IR) and hence mixed together and chromatographed over alumina. The benzene eluted fractions gave a solid which on repeated crystallisation furnished another crop of β-sitosterol (from mixed m.p., TLC and IR spectrum). Other fractions were found to be a mixture of

several components of nearly same polarity and hence it was not possible to separate them by repeated chromatographic resolution or by crystallisation.

Further work on the characterisation of the ketone, m.p. 78°, alcohol, m.p. 56°, hydrocarbon A, hydrocarbon B and hydrocarbon C is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.s and b.p.s are uncorrected. The UV spectra were recorded in ethanol solution on Beckmann DK-II Spectrophotometer, the IR spectra on a Perkin Elmer infra-red spectrophotometer, Model 137B and Model 221 in nujol mull and the NMR spectra were run on Varian instrument (60 MC) in CCl_4 using tetramethylsilane as internal standard. The GLC analyses were carried out on a Griffin and George VPC apparatus MK IIa with polyester column employing hydrogen as carrier gas. The acid washed activated alumina standardised as per Brockmann's procedure was employed for column chromatography. Silica gel mixture used for TLC contained 85% of silica gel and 15% of plaster of paris (200 mesh). Petroleum ether refers to the fraction b.p. 40–60°.

Extractives of Artemisia vulgaris: The whole dried plant of *Artemisia vulgaris* L. (37 kg.) was extracted with petroleum ether at room temperature using an efficient mechanical stirrer. Six repeated extractions were carried out. The combined pet. ether extracts (393.1) were then concentrated at 40° under reduced pressure to afford a semisolid mass (1.3 kg) which is named as "Oil of Artemisia"; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{nujol}}$ 3490, 1700 (w)*, 1730, 1664, 1408, 1240, 1160 and 1020 cm^{-1} .

Isolation of Ketone, m.p. 78°: The oil of artemisia (1.3 kg) was treated with methanol (2 l.) and kept at -15° for 2 days; the resulting solid was washed with chilled acetone and crystallised from chloroform-acetone mixture. The solid (170 g.) obtained was chromatographed over alumina (Grade III, 1.5 g.). The pet. ether eluted material on crystallisation from ethylacetate afforded white amorphous solid, m.p. 78°, $[\alpha]_D + 0^\circ$, (C, 2.0): $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{nujol}}$: 1724, 1408, 1200, 1190, 1175 and 920 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 82.02; H, 14.06%).

TABLE I

Chromatography of Oil of Artemisia after the separation of ketone, m.p. 78°
Wt. of oil: 500 g.; Wt. of alumina (Grade III): 5.5 kg.

Fractions	Eluents	Amount of eluate (in litres)	Weight (g)	Remarks
A	Pet. ether	2	10	Hydrocarbons.
B	„	30	254	IR band for carbonyl (1735 cm^{-1}) group.
C	Pet. ether ; Benzene (1 : 1)	15	22	IR bands for carbonyl (1735 cm^{-1}) and hydroxyl (3472 cm^{-1}) groups.
D	Benzene and then alcohol.	20	20	„

* w is the abbreviation of weak.

Isolation of Hydrocarbon A, m.p. 64°: The fraction A (Table I) was subjected to fractional distillation under vacuum upto 180° (bath/0.2 mm) but no pure compounds could be obtained (TLC and VPC). The residue left after distillation crystallised from ethyl acetate solution when kept at 0° for 2 days. Repeated crystallisations from pet. ether at 0° afforded silvery white needles, m.p. 64° [α]_D±0° (C, 1.33). (Found: C, 85.33; H, 14.86%).

TABLE II

Chromatography of Fraction B₁₀ obtained after the separation of Ketone, m.p. 78° from Fraction B. Wt. of fraction : 210 g.; Wt. of alumina (Grade II) : 5.3 kg.

Fractions	Eluents	Amount of eluate (in litres)	Weight(g)	Remarks
B ₂	Pet. ether	7	125	IR bands for carbonyl (1745 cm ⁻¹) group.
B ₃	„	7	8	IR bands for carbonyl (1724 cm ⁻¹) and hydroxy (3448 cm ⁻¹) groups.
B ₄	Pet. ether : benzene (1 : 1).	12	20	„
B ₅	Benzene and then alcohol.	15	27	IR bands for hydroxyl (3445 cm ⁻¹) group.

TABLE III

Extraction of Fraction B₂ (125 g.)

Fractions	Bath temp.°	Pressure (in mm)	Weight (g)	Remarks
B ₆	100—140	20	13.5	IR bands for carbonyl (1475 cm ⁻¹) group.
B ₇	100—140	2.5	10.0	„
B ₈	200—205	0.3	23.5	IR bands for carbonyl (1724 cm ⁻¹) and hydroxyl (3497 cm ⁻¹) groups.
B ₉	220—270	0.25	5.5	Hydrocarbons.
B ₁₀			65	IR bands for acetoxyl (1740, 1250 cm ⁻¹) groups.

VPC of B₆ and B₇ : Identification of α -Pinene, β -Pinene and Thujone. Column : polyester; temperature : 130°; hydrogen flow : 4.5 l./hr.; current: 150 M amp.

From the GLC analysis, the fraction B₆ seems to be a mixture of at least six compounds having retention time (i) 1 min. 15 secs.; (ii) 2 mins.; (iii) 3 min. 30 secs.; (iv) 4 min. 4 secs.; (v) 8 min. 50 secs.; (vi) 11 min. 40 secs. Of these nos. (i), (ii) and (v) were identified as α -pinene, β -pinene and thujone by comparing their retention time with standard samples. The other three could not be identified. The fraction B₇ contained 88% of thujone along with other components present in the fraction B₆.

Semicarbazone of Fraction B₇: Fraction B₇ (1 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (20 ml) and heated on a steam bath. It formed a semicarbazone which on repeated crystallisations afforded needles, m.p. 186–88°, $[\alpha]_D + 58^\circ$ (C, 2.92) (Lit.²⁰ records for (–) thujone semicarbazone: m.p. 186–88°, $[\alpha]_D + 58.5^\circ$), (Found: C, 63.15; H, 9.20; N, 20.01, Calc. for C₄H₁₉ON₃: C, 63.15; H, 9.15; N, 20.08%).

2,4-Dinitrophenyl hydrazone of Fraction B₇: Fraction B₇ (0.1 g.) yielded 2:4-DNPH which separated out as yellow crystalline solid. On repeated crystallisations it afforded crystals, m.p. 116°, $[\alpha]_D + 44^\circ$ (C, 0.5) (Lit.²⁰ records for 2.4 DNPH of (–) thujone, m.p. 117°, $[\alpha]_D + 44^\circ$) (Found: C, 55.94; H, 6.20; N, 19.35; Calc. for: C₁₆H₂₀O₄N₄: C, 57.82; H, 6.07, N, 19.26%).

Potassium permanganate oxidation of Fraction B₇: Fraction B₇ (1 g.) was oxidised according to Thompson's procedure¹⁴ to give the crystalline keto carboxylic acid (IV), m.p. 75–76°, $[\alpha]_D + 210^\circ$ (C, 1.2) n_{max}^{25} : 3448, 3125, 2632, 1695, 1176, 1093, 1048, 1020, 995 and 952 cm⁻¹, (Lit.¹⁴: m.p. 75–76°, $[\alpha]_D + 214^\circ$) (Found: C, 63.65; H, 8.31. C₉H₁₄O₃ requires: C, 63.57; H, 8.29%). Mixed m.p. of the above keto acid remained undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample prepared by KMnO₄-oxidation of authentic (+) isothujone. Further confirmation of their identity was provided by superimposable IR spectra and same R_f in TLC with an authentic sample (Both showed same R_f 0.5 with methylenechloride, ethylacetate and acetic acid (10:4:1%) as a solvent phase under identical conditions).

Regeneration of (–) thujone from its semicarbazone by oxalic acid: Pure (–) thujone semicarbazone (m.p. 186–88° $[\alpha]_D + 58^\circ$; 780 mg) dissolved in alcohol (5 ml) was treated with oxalic acid (4.8 g. in 40 ml. of water) and pet. ether (50 ml.). The mixture was refluxed for 4 hr.; the pet. ether (2 × 50 ml.) and the combined pet. ether extracts, after washing with water, was dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was removed and the residue distilled at 100–110° (bath/5) mm to give thujone (200 mg), having the following properties: $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$, (C, 1.5), n_D^{25} 1.445 (lit²⁰: (–) thujone: $[\alpha]_D - 20^\circ$; n_D^{15} 1.449 and (+) isothujone: $[\alpha]_D + 72^\circ$; n_D^{25} 1.450). (Found: C, 79.22; H, 10.70; Calc. for C₁₀H₁₆O: C, 78.99; H, 10.59%).

Regeneration of (–) thujone from its semicarbazone by sulphuric acid: A mixture of pure (–) thujone semicarbazone (730 mg), 2(N) H₂SO₄ (7.1 ml) and pet. ether (50 ml) was stirred at 20–24° for 4 days and filtered. The aqueous portion was extracted with pet. ether (2 × 50 ml). The combined pet. ether extracts were dried (K₂CO₃) and solvent removed. The residue was distilled at 100–110°/5 mm to give pure (–) thujone (280 mg). $[\alpha]_D - 20^\circ$ (C, 2.05), n_D^{25} 1.448. It showed a single peak in VPC. (Found: C, 78.90; H, 10.61; Calc. for C₁₀H₁₆O: C, 78.89; H, 10.59%).

Similarly pure (+) isothujone semicarbazone, m.p. 172°, $[\alpha]_D + 220^\circ$. (0.370 g.), under identical conditions described above afforded pure (+) isothujone (0.13 g.) b.p. 100–120° (bath)/5 mm. $[\alpha]_D + 72^\circ$, n_D^{25} 1.450. (Found: C, 79.1; H, 10.45; Calc. for C₁₀H₁₆O: C, 78.89; H, 10.59%).

Isolation of alcohol, m.p. 56° : The fraction B₈ (Table III) was kept in pet. ether at 0° for 2 days; the solid separated after crystallisation from pet. ether afforded crystals, m.p. 56°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$ (C, 1.01). It showed a single spot in TLC (R_f 0.36) with 10% ethylacetate in pet. ether as a solvent phase; under identical conditions authentic patchouli alcohol showed R_f 0.71. In VPC the compound from B₈ fraction showed a single peak having retention time 4 min. 30 secs.; under identical conditions patchouli alcohol showed retention time 1 min. 45 secs. IR (nujol) bands at : 3344, 1064, 1042, 1020, 1001, 980, 970 and 890 cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 80.2; H, 14.24; C-CH₃, 3.46%). The alcohol was resistant to oxidation in acetone solution with Jones chromic acid reagent¹⁷ or by chromic acid in pyridine¹⁸ solution.

Acetate of the Alcohol, m.p. 56° : A mixture of alcohol (60 mg.), acetic anhydride (1 ml) and pyridine (10 ml) was kept at 40° for 24 hr., cooled, poured in crushed ice and extracted with ether. After washing with dilute HCl (4 times), then water, it was dried (Na₂SO₄) and chromatographed over alumina (Grade II), (2 g.). Elution with pet. ether furnished the acetate (45 mg), b.p. 150–70° (bath)/2 m.m. It showed a single spot in TLC (R_f 0.45) with 40% benzene in pet. ether as a solvent phase; under identical conditions the starting alcohol showed R_f 0.25. IR (nujol) bands at 1745, 1235, and 1042 cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 77.10; H, 12.24%).

Isolation of Hydrocarbon B : The mother liquor (B₁₁) after the separation of alcohol, m.p. 56°, was subjected to fractional distillation and the fraction, b.p. 140–65° (bath)/0.3 mm. (14 g.) was chromatographed over alumina (Grade I, 500 g.) and eluted as usual. The middle cut of the pet. ether fractions on distillation over sodium afforded the hydrocarbon B, b.p. 130–40° (bath)/0.3 mm., $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$, (C, 1.05), n_D^{27} 1.469. It showed a single spot in TLC on silica gel/AgNO₃²¹ plate with pet. ether as a solvent phase and showed a single peak in VPC having retention time 1 min. 20 secs. Under identical conditions longifolene showed retention time 24 secs. IR bands were observed at 2950, 1453, 1372 and 830 cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 87.06; H, 12.75%).

Isolation of Hydrocarbon C : The fraction B₉ (5 g) was chromatographed over alumina (Grade I, 300 g.). The middle cut of the pet. ether fractions on distillation over sodium afforded the hydrocarbon C, b.p. 140–50° (bath)/0.5 mm., $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$, n_D^{27} 1.458. It showed a single spot in TLC on silica gel/AgNO₃²¹ plate with pet. ether as a solvent phase and showed a single peak in VPC having retention time 1 min. 30 secs. Under identical conditions longifolene showed retention time 24 secs. (IR bands at 2941, 1639, 1587, 1370, 1365, 990, 980, 900 and 892 cm⁻¹). (Found : C, 86.7; H, 13.42%).

Isolation of α -Amyrin acetate : The undistilled residue (B₁₀) (65 g.) was chromatographed over alumina (Grade I, 2.5 kg) and eluted as usual. The pet. ether eluted fraction (2 l.) afforded several hydrocarbons. The pet. ether-benzene (1 : 1 v/v) eluted fractions (4.l) afforded a solid which on repeated crystallisation from methanol-methylene chloride and finally with ethylacetate afforded shining crystals of α -amyrin acetate, m.p. 223–24°, $[\alpha]_D + 78^\circ$ (C, 0.68) (Lit.²², m.p. 225–26°, $[\alpha]_D + 77^\circ$) (Found : M⁺ 468 and C, 82.4; H, 11.05. C₃₂H₅₂O₂ (468) requires : C, 81.99; H, 11.18%).

21. Sukh Dev and A. S. Gupta, *J. Chromatog.*, 1963, **12**, 189.

22. T. G. Halsall and T. R. Alpin, *Fortschr. Chem. Organ. Naturstoffe*, 1964, **22**, 153.

Hydrolysis of α -Amyrin acetate : A mixture of α -amyrin acetate (60 mg), KOH (1.2 g) and methanol (60 ml) on refluxing for 4 hr. and working up by the usual procedure afforded pure α -amyrin, m.p. 186–87°, $[\alpha]_D + 86^\circ$ (C, 0.8) (Lit.²², m.p. 186°, $[\alpha]_D + 83^\circ$). (Found : Mol. wt. by mass spectrometry : 426 and C, 42.52; H, 11.69. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O$ (426) : C, 84.44; H, 11.81%).

Isolation of Fernenol : The alcohol-eluted fraction (B_{21}) (10 g) from the chromatography of fraction B_{10} , was re-chromatographed over alumina (Grade II, 700 g) and eluted following the usual procedure (vide supra). The benzene-eluted fractions afforded a solid which on repeated crystallisation from absolute methanol afforded fernenol¹⁹, m.p. 194°, $[\alpha]_D - 24^\circ$ (C, 0.65). The mother liquor after crystallisation of fernenol was evaporated to dryness and was converted to its acetate by Ac_2O -pyridine. The crude acetate, m.p. 175–85° was saponified to the alcohol with 5% alcoholic KOH, chromatographed over alumina (Grade III, 20 g). The pet. ether eluted fernenol which on repeated crystallisations from absolute methanol furnished more fernenol, m.p. 194°, $[\alpha]_D - 24^\circ$.

Isolation of α -Amyrin : The mother liquor (B_{24}) after the crystallisation of fernenol was converted to its acetate by the usual method after removal of methanol; the crude acetate was chromatographed over alumina (Grade III, 10 g) and eluted with pet. ether. The solid obtained on repeated crystallisation from ethylacetate furnished shining crystals, m.p. 223–24°, $[\alpha]_D + 78^\circ$, characterised as α -amyrin acetate on the basis of mixed m.p., identical R_f in TLC and superimposable IR spectra.

Isolation of Stigmasterol : The combined fractions of B_4 and C (Chart I, 42 g) on keeping with ethylacetate (50 ml) at -15° for 2 days afforded a sticky solid which on repeated crystallisation from ethylacetate and finally alcohol furnished crystals of stigmasterol, m.p. 170°, $[\alpha]_D - 50^\circ$ (C, 0.65) (Lit.²³, m.p. 170°, $[\alpha]_D - 51^\circ$) (Found : C, 84.42; H, 11.68. Calc. for $C_{29}H_{48}O$: C, 84.40; H, 11.72%).

Stigmasterol, isolated from *Artemisia vulgaris* L. on acetylation with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate under usual conditions afforded the acetate m.p. 144–45°, $[\alpha]_D - 55^\circ$ (C, 0.9), identical with stigmasterol acetate on the basis of mixed m.p., identical R_f in TLC and superimposable IR spectra.

Isolation of β -sitosterol : The mother liquor (C_1 , 25 g) left after the separation of stigmasterol was chromatographed over alumina (Grade II, 1 kg) and eluted as usual. The pet. ether-benzene (1 : 1, v/v) eluted fractions contained some carbonyl components (from IR). The benzene eluted fraction yielded a solid which on repeated crystallisations afforded another crop of fernenol (100 g.), m.p. 194°, $[\alpha]_D - 24^\circ$. The benzene-chloroform (1 : 1, v/v) eluted fractions furnished a crystalline solid which on repeated crystallisations from methanol yielded crystals, m.p. 136–37°, $[\alpha]_D - 35^\circ$ (C, 0.68) (Lit.²³ records for β -sitosterol : m.p. 136–37°, $[\alpha]_D - 35^\circ$). It showed a single spot in TLC with 20% ethylacetate in benzene as a solvent phase (R_f 0.45); under identical conditions stigmasterol showed R_f 0.44 (Found : C, 84.02; H, 12.22; Calc. for $C_{29}H_{50}O$: C, 83.99; H, 12.15%). The combined formations of

23. S. A. Heilborn, Dictionary of Organic Compounds.

B₅ and D (Chart I, 45 g) were chromatographed over alumina (Grade III, 600 g) and eluted with the solvents and solvent mixtures the sequence of which being shown in Table II. The benzene eluted fractions (1-10 fractions collected in 100 ml. each) gave β -sitosterol, identified by mixed m.p., identical R_f in TLC and superimposable IR spectra with authentic samples. The later fractions were highly viscous and alcoholic (from IR) in nature. In TLC, they seemed to be a mixture of several components. Further purification of this mixture could not be achieved.

The authors acknowledge their sincere thanks to the Director, National Chemical Laboratory, Poona for providing laboratory facilities, Professors S. C. Bhattacharyya and Dr. K. K. Chakravarti for their interest in this investigation and to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, India for financial support to one of them (S.K.K.).

Department of Pure Chemistry,
University College of Science,
Calcutta-9.

and

National Chemical Laboratory
Poona-8.

Received December 2, 1967.